

西安交通大学
XI'AN JIAOTONG UNIVERSITY

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Additive Manufacturing of Advanced Fiber Reinforced Composites and Applications

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Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, China**

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Additive Manufacturing of Advanced Fiber Reinforced Composites and Applications

Research background

3D printing for AFRCs

Structural innovation

Summary

Research background

- Carbon fiber reinforced composites are used in the field of automobile, aircraft, and space

大众XL1使用了大量的碳纤维材质，
全车重量仅为795千克。

Automobile

Aircraft

昵图网 www.nipic.com

By:bigduke No.20120828154429589187

Space

Research background

- Carbon fiber reinforced composites are used in the field of automobile, aircraft, and space

A350 testing fuselage

Sources: www.airliners.de
World Market News Nr. 439

Light weight applications A350XWB

Research background

- Carbon fiber reinforced composites are used in the field of automobile, aircraft, and space

20-25% cost reduction
25-30% weight reduction

Source: www.nasa.gov

All-composite liquid hydrogen tanks

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Research background

- **Fiber placement system in Xi'an Jiaotong University**

Robot system with the capability for fiber placement with four tows

Research background

- Composites are light weight and high performance, but high cost for fabrication

Source: VW AG

Research background

- **Composites are light weight and high performance, but high cost for fabrication**

Teijin's electric concept car demonstrator has a cabin structure made entirely of carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite.

**End-of-Life Vehicles (ELV)
directive requiring 85% of a
vehicle to be reused or
recycled by 2015**

Council directive 2000/53/EC (End-of-Life Vehicles).

**From thermosetting to
thermoplastic composites**

Stewart Richard, Reinforced plastics, 2011, 3(55) 22-28

Research background

- 3D printing of composites could reduce the fabrication cost and increase the process flexibility, for example FDM or SLS process.

Freeform process without moulds
Integrated fabrication of complex components

Expand application

Schematic of FDM process

3D printed short fiber reinforced composite
components

Research background

- 3D printed short fiber reinforced composites might only provide a very limited improvement of mechanical performance.

Short fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites using FDM

Research background

- 3D printing for Advanced Fiber Reinforced Composites (AFRC) with much higher performance is a critical development direction for AM.

Research background

- Understanding of relationships among materials, processes, structures, and functions is the driving force for innovations on composite 3D printing

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3D printing for CFRTPCs

- Innovation on processes could realize the fabrication of continuous fiber reinforced composites with high performance and low cost

Conventional fiber placement

High cost, complex process
Simple shape forming
Thermal set plastics

Fused deposition modelling (FDM)

Thermal plastics
Short Fiber reinforced composites

3D printing of continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTPCs)

Composite preparation + Forming by 3D printing

Interdisciplinary frontier

3D printing for CFRTPCs

● Integrated preparation and forming for CFRTPCs

Mechanism for 3D printing of CFRTPCs

3D printing for CFRTPCs

● Integrated preparation and forming for CFRTPCs

Experimental device of 3D printing for CFRTPCs

3D printing for CFRTPCs

- Mechanical properties of CFRTPCs were controllable by adjusting the process parameters

Using PLA as matrix, and 1K carbon fiber as reinforcement

3D printing for CFRTPCs

- Mechanical properties of CFRTPCs were controllable by adjusting the process parameters- interface

Microstructures of the fractured cross sections in CFRTPCs

3D printing for CFRTPCs

- Mechanical properties of CFRTPCs were controllable by adjusting the process parameters- fiber content

3D printing for CFRTPCs

- Composite structures have been successfully fabricated by 3D printing of CFRTPCs

3D printed Cf/PLA composite parts

3D printing for CFRTPCs

- Composite structures have been successfully fabricated by 3D printing of CFRTPCs

3D printed Cf/PLA composite parts

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3D printing for CFRTPCs

● 3D printing machine for CFRTPCs are now available for market

FiberTech

3D printer for high performance plastics (**Peek**) and fiber reinforced composites (**Cf/PLA**),

$T_{\text{printing head}} \sim 400^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{\text{at}} \sim 200^{\circ}\text{C}$

Patent ZL2014103256503.3

Recycling and remanufacturing of 3D printed composites

- Remelt PLA matrix along reverse printing path and pulling out continuous fiber bundle from the composite part, and then reuse the fiber filament

Recycling and remanufacturing of 3D printed composites

- Remelt PLA matrix along reverse printing path and pulling out continuous fiber bundle from the composite part, and then reuse the fiber filament

(1) Melt-Extraction

Original printed CFRTPCs part

(2) Mold reforming

Recycled impregnated filament

(3) CFRTPCs reprinting

Remanufactured CFRTPCs part

Fully recycling and remanufacturing of CFRTPCs

Recycling and remanufacturing of 3D printed composites

- Remanufacturing process led to about 25% improvement on the flexural strength over the originally printed composites specimens

Mechanical strength and modulus of pure PLA, originally printed and re-manufactured composites specimens

Recycling and remanufacturing of 3D printed composites

- A four-“Re” cleaner production pattern for 3D printed CFRTPCs

Oral: 376-Manufacturing and recycling of 3D printed continuous carbon fiber reinforced PLA composites
-16:35, 23 August-ROOM19 (VIP102)

Powder bed fusion for short-fiber reinforced composites

- SLS process can fabricate polymer composites with any complex structures and controllable properties

Selective laser sintering (SLS)

Carbon fiber reinforced nylon parts

Powder bed fusion for short fiber reinforced composites

- Multiphase material composition determines the absorption and transmission in the powder bed, thus influence the properties and accuracy of the fabricated components

Specific heat of composite vs. temperature

Transmitted laser power along the layer thickness

Powder bed fusion for short fiber reinforced composites

- Heat affect zone (HAZ) was influenced by the material properties, and determine the chosing of process parameters, e.g. layer thickness, hatch spacing

Simulation parameters:

Lase power 10W

Scanning speed 3500mm/s

※ Yellow region is the fusion zone, heat affect zone (HAZ)

Temperature distribution in the cross section

Powder bed fusion for short fiber reinforced composites

- Mechanical properties were improved by reinforced phase, and extra function (e.g. porosity) could also be obtained by tailoring the powder composition

* Porous PA could be obtained by dissolving the NaCl powder in the NaCl/PA composite

Powder bed fusion for short fiber reinforced composites

- However, weak bonding between adjacent layers makes materials anisotropic and limits industrial applications of SLS composites.

Poster: p1102-33
Selective Laser
Sintering of
Polyamide 12
Composites

SEM pictures of cross sections in samples prepared along X, Y, Z directions, respectively

Powder bed fusion for short fiber reinforced composites

- **CASE STUDY:** Light-weight parts can be designed and fabricated for some non-critical situations, e.g. apparatus support

Apparatus support designed
for the usage in rocket

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Source: VW AG

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Curvilinear fiber orientation by 3D printing with MDOF

- Few advantages were taken by using MDOF system to realize the 3D printing process for CFRTPCs

3D printing process on a robotic system

Source: X. Tian et al, AMT (under review), Patent: ZL201410325554.9

Curvilinear fiber orientation by 3D printing with MDOF

- First, 3D printing on a curved surface can improve the surface roughness

Staircase effect and lamination weakness problems of flat-layer 3D printing

3D printing on curved layers

Curvilinear fiber orientation by 3D printing with MDOF

- First, 3D printing on a curved surface can improve the surface roughness

Reduce the stare-case effect

Curvilinear fiber orientation by 3D printing with MDOF

- Second, 3D printing on a curved surface can improve interlamination bonding strength, and overall structural stiffness

Structural stiffness and failure load with different paths

Curvilinear fiber orientation by 3D printing with MDOF

- Third, fiber orientation can be tailored precisely according to the stress distribution to minimize the stress concentration

3D printing for lightweight composite structures

- Controllable distribution of continuous fiber through path design provides a new way for the integrated fabrication of complexly shaped CFRCLSs

Panel-core debonding failure

Common failure mode

Overlapping model

CFRCLSs : Continuous Fibre Reinforced Composite Lightweight Structures

3D printing for lightweight composite structures

- Elastic buckling, plastic deformation, and fracturing of the corrugated-core were the dominant failure modes in the printed CFRCLs.

Compression stress-strain curves

Failure mode of the printed CFRCLs

3D printing for lightweight composite structures

- Mechanical properties of CFRCLs were controllable by adjusting the process parameters and structural parameters

Influence of cell length on the compressive property

Influence of layer thickness on the compressive property

3D printing for lightweight composite structures

- When the fibre content was 11.5 % vol, the 3D printed spline corrugated-core CFRCLSs achieved a compression strength of 17.17 MPa.

Fiber: Kevlar fiber (linear density of 145 dtex, density of 1440 Kg/m³)

Matrix: Polylactide (PLA/1.75 mm, density of 1240 Kg/m³)

Comparison of the compression strength

3D printing for lightweight composite structures

- **CASE STUDY: Integrated manufacturing of composite lightweight structure with complex shapes**

Lightweight sandwich structure

Heterogeneous lightweight sandwich structure

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Exploration on 3D printing processes and applications for Advanced Fiber Reinforced Composites

Research background

3D printing for AFRCs

Structural innovation

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Summary

- **3D printing for advanced composites is a critical development trend for both AM and composite fields**
- **Multi-functions, multi-scales, and multi-materials integrated fabrication is the development direction for composites AM**
 - e.g. 3D printed composites with controllable EMI shielding effects
- **Understanding the relationships among materials, process, structure, and functions is important to innovation**
 - e.g. Interface modification to achieve 3D printing of metallic composites
- **Interdisciplinary innovation must be the driving force for the success of future scientific research and industrial application**
 - e.g. 3D printing for aerospace, or in space is pushing the development of advanced materials, processes, and equipment.

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Thank you for your attention.

Questions ?

